

D5.5

**Interim
Stakeholders
consultation report**

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1 Executive summary

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D5.5 “Interim Stakeholders Consultation report” in the framework of the ITD 4.7, WP5, Task 5.2 of Shift2MaaS project (S2R-OC-IP4-02-2018). The Shift2MaaS consortium identifies the importance of the participation and involvement of key stakeholders during all the phases of the project.

More specifically, this deliverable provides:

- An explicit list of the stakeholders for the Stakeholder’s group in Chapter 5;
- A report on the stakeholder’s workshop focused on MaaS organised by Shift2MaaS and other related projects (Chapter 6);
- Clarifications on the formation of the stakeholder’s group on a continuous basis within the lifetime of the project (Chapter 7).

The work with Shift2MaaS stakeholders will be continued until the end of the project, so the outcomes of this work will be included in D5.6 Final Stakeholders consultation report and additional use-cases.

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2 Abbreviations and acronyms

CP	Carpooling Providers
IM	Infrastructure Manager
ITD	Integrated Technical Demonstration
MaaS	Mobility-as-a-Service
PTA	Public Transport Authorities
PTO	Public Transport Operators
SSP	Sharing Schemes Providers
TEP	Travel Event Provider
TOA	Transport Organising Authorities
TrSP	Travel Service Provider
TSP	Transport Service Provider
WP	Work Package

3 Background

The present document constitutes the Deliverable D5.5 “Interim Stakeholders Consultation report” in the framework of the ITD 4.7, WP5, Task 5.2 of Shift2MaaS project (S2R-OC-IP4-02-2018).

It contributes as well to ITD 4.7, WP2 T2.2 “Definition of scenarios for the demonstration sites” and T2.3 “Definition of use-cases for the demonstration sites”.

4 Objectives/aim

The Shift2MaaS consortium recognises the importance of the participation and involvement of key stakeholders during all the phases of the project. The first workshop was organised in the frame of UITP Summit in Stockholm at the beginning of the project in M7 (12 June 2019) in order to present the work that is planned to relevant stakeholders.

Task 5.2, under which this report was issued and the mentioned workshop was organised, aims to assist in the formation of a stakeholders group. This will be the project's key group helping in the design and implementation of future use-cases and potential demonstrations of IP4 technologies.

Thus, the outcomes of WP5 will feed T2.2 and T2.3 of Shift2MaaS as the key stakeholders can collaborate with the Shift2MaaS consortium to better define and assess the use-cases of Shift2MaaS. Shift2MaaS will organise a workshop in M12 for the IP4 projects in order to share and promote collaboration at all levels.

Furthermore, Shift2MaaS will facilitate discussions that aim to set the pillars of collaboration among policy/decision-makers, transport operators and academics. This collaboration will support the translation of theoretical frameworks which promote seamless transport, into successful use-cases of practical implementation through the demonstrations of Shift2MaaS.

More specifically, this deliverable reports on the outcomes of the first stakeholder workshop and consultation that feed the T2.2 and T2.3 of Shift2MaaS.

5 Identification of the stakeholders for the Stakeholder's group

This chapter is a first attempt to define the stakeholders of the Shift2MaaS project. This list will be updated and enhanced throughout the project. The stakeholders' identification was based on issues related to the project scope of works, objectives and previous consultations carried out under similar transport topics. The below points represent inputs for the identification of the stakeholders:

- The results of the GOF4R project, more specifically, D2.2: Analysis of the demand of market actors for the Interoperability Framework¹;
- UITP terms and definitions;
- Shift2Rail stakeholders.

Type of a stakeholder	Description and key characteristics
Transport organising authorities (TOA)	<p>A government or public agency created to perform a single function or restricted group of related activities. The authority pertains to the government entity that is responsible for the organisation of the public transport market. It is responsible for transport fare level, route designations and other public transport operating system policies, supervision, regulation and award of operating contracts and franchises. In some cases, the transport operating company and the authority are within the same government unit and perform policy, regulatory, planning, and operating functions. In other cases, the authority is a separate public agency that does not have any operating responsibilities, but establishes public transport system policies and acts as the system's regulator².</p> <p>TOA can set up the rules at various territorial levels: local (e.g., city-level), national (e.g., country level), European or International for a sustainable mobility and interested in developing an overall market framework and especially an Interoperability Framework facilitating an increase in the use of multimodal seamless mobility solutions combining several travel services.</p>
Transport service provider (TSP)	<p>An individual or an entity, such as a corporation or a partnership, in the business of providing public transport services against payment by the passengers and/or the authority³.</p> <p>TSP is responsible for delivering the transport service and managing the drivers and the operating staff.</p>

¹ Available at: <http://www.gof4r.eu/download.aspx?id=0b22ea5a-4ad1-432c-abaf-0d9dcdea3792>

² UITP Glossary of public transport terms – Last update : February 2014

³ UITP Glossary of public transport terms – Last update : February 2014

Infrastructure Manager (IM)	IM is a body responsible for establishing and maintaining infrastructure. It may also include the management of infrastructure control and safety systems. At the urban scale, it may often be a case that TSP and IM roles are accomplished by the same company.
Sharing schemes providers (SSP)	One-way-capable rental offer in public spaces, for several target groups, with network characteristics ⁴ . SSP is a complementary mode of transport.
Carpooling providers (CP)	An arrangement where two or more people share the use and cost of privately-owned vehicles when travelling together to and from pre-arranged destinations ⁵ . CP is a complementary mode of transport.
Demand responsive (or dial-a-ride) service	Such a service is run with passenger cars, vans or small buses operating in response to calls from passengers to the public transport operator, who then dispatches a vehicle to pick up the passengers and transport them to their destinations. A demand responsive operation is characterised by the following: (a) The vehicles do not operate over a fixed route or on a fixed schedule except, perhaps, on a temporary basis to satisfy a special need; and (b) typically, the vehicle may be dispatched to pick up several passengers at different pick-up points before taking them to their respective destinations and may even be interrupted on route to these destinations to pick up other passengers. These services could be required by law for persons with disabilities and others not able to use fixed-route services ⁶ .
Retailer, Travel Agency, Distributor	Tickets resellers and third-party retailers. They can provide both offline and online services.
MaaS providers	One-stop-shop for mobility services with pay-per-use or other payment schemes (e.g., monthly subscriptions). MaaS Providers offer different transport options, be they public transport, ride-, car- or bike-sharing, taxi or car rental/lease, or a combination thereof.
Travel service provider (TrSP)	Offering travel services (very often online), especially but not exclusively on transportation, e.g., providing travel data or other services as a third party. TrSP can provide the following services to the customers: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Journey planning; • Offer building; • Trip tricking; • Travel companion.
Travel Event Provider (TEP)	TEP is a service that provides some events to the user based on his/her location.

⁴ UITP Glossary of public transport terms – Last update : February 2014

⁵ UITP Glossary of public transport terms – Last update : February 2014

⁶ UITP Glossary of public transport terms – Last update : February 2014

Payment service providers	e.g. Visa, MasterCard, PayPal
International associations	Representing the interest of major stakeholders per mode (air, rail, public transport) including passengers associations.
JU S2R members	Both founding and associated members
Official European regulatory institutions	Official institutions which are deciding on technical documents specifying mandatory requirements in order to achieve better functioning of the market in a specific domain, which are normally leading to standardisation based on a mandate (e.g. EC, ERA)
Other relevant EU-funded research projects	The projects related to MaaS topic, travel companion and IT solutions for the better travel experience

Table 1: List of Shift2MaaS stakeholders for the Stakeholder's group

6 Stakeholders workshop on MaaS technologies

6.1 Scope of the workshop

The workshop was organised by five EU-funded projects (i.e., Shift2MaaS⁷ (in collaboration with COHESIVE⁸), IMOVE⁹, Galileo4Mobility¹⁰, My-TRAC¹¹, and SMARTE¹²) at the UITP Summit 2019¹³. The objectives of the workshop were:

- Bringing together MaaS experts and EU-funded projects in order to establish connections for potential future collaborations;
- Discuss essential topics on MaaS: barriers and solutions.

Agenda of the session can be found in Appendix 1.

The session was opened by a key-note speech of Martin Röhrleef, Head of Mobility Innovation, ÜSTRA where he presented MaaS concepts and outcomes from the recently issued UITP Policy Brief: *'Ready for MaaS? Accelerating easier mobility for citizens and better data for cities'*¹⁴.

All five projects demonstrated the latest developments and advanced solutions for enhancing MaaS deployment and operation at EU level.

The next part of the session was a discussion in round tables. Every participant could choose a table corresponding to his/her expertise or specific interest. The four topics were technical enablers & barriers, business models & market uptake strategies, sustainability impacts & assessment, and data-sharing.

The last part of the session was a panel discussion, where the moderators of each table and Shift2Rail IP4 programme manager Esther Bravo shared the outcomes of the discussions.

Pictures from the event are in Appendix 7.

6.2 Uniqueness of EU-funded projects

All projects are focused on different aspects of MaaS deployment. The **COHESIVE** project is focused on the integration of Shift2Rail IT technologies¹⁵ in a single integrated solution, while the complementary **Shift2MaaS** project co-designs and validates scenarios for the deployment of these solutions, organises their demonstrations in three European sites and assesses their impact focusing on regulatory and behavioural aspects. **IMOVE** is focused on developing and testing business models for MaaS, frameworks for market uptake, and boosting user engagement. **Galileo4Mobility** is exploring opportunities to improve MaaS schemes through the application of Galileo satellite technology¹⁶. The **My-TRAC** project presented

⁷ <http://shift2maas.eu/>

⁸ https://projects.shift2rail.org/s2r_ip4_n.aspx?p=COHESIVE

⁹ <https://www.imove-project.eu/>

¹⁰ <http://www.galileo4mobility.eu/>

¹¹ <http://www.my-trac.eu/>

¹² <http://www.smarte-rail.eu/>

¹³ <https://uitpsummit.org/>

¹⁴ https://www.uitp.org/sites/default/files/cck-focus-papers-files/Policy%20Brief_MaaS_V3_final_web_0.pdf

¹⁵ <https://shift2rail.org/research-development/ip4/>

¹⁶ Galileo satellite system

its application that combines behavioural transport analytics and artificial intelligence (AI) algorithms for the seamless integration of services. Finally, **SMARTE** showed the user-centric approach and how the travellers' experience influences public transport development.

6.3 Key outcomes and ideas of the discussion

Nowadays, when there are plenty of local use-cases and schemes demonstrating the capabilities of MaaS, it is important to focus on a large scale 'glocal' (global/local) MaaS deployment at EU level and beyond, creating an interoperable travel experience. One of the main problems with fighting car ownership is that the opportunities for the first-and-last-miles are not yet attractive enough.

The next important step in MaaS development is a specification of existing services. For example, personalisation of combined tickets and other services may help to solve the problem of disproportionate distribution of passengers' flows.

Balance of solutions between shared vehicles and MaaS transit and alternatives for PRMs¹⁷ should be important aspects of MaaS design. Mass transit public transport will remain in the heart of the system. The following years, the focus also will be on premium MaaS services.

Legislation for data-sharing is still an important aspect for MaaS market uptake.

Opportunities for further research and analysis:

- Blockchain for managing the distribution of revenues from ticket sales and other transactions;
- Web of transportation (the interoperability framework) for the creation of 'glocal' solutions;
- Gamification of solutions for fostering modal shift.

Existing barriers for the uptake of MaaS schemes:

- Slow uptake by private enterprises due to lack of funding;
- Usage of real-time data. Such data is still considered as a competitive advantage, and some operators may fear to disclose it to other operators and Transport Service Providers (TSPs);
- A risk that aggregated data can be exploited on the private side (e.g., be sold to third parties);
- There is passengers' reluctance of sharing data, but at the same time there are high expectations for services that require the data;
- Existing frameworks that support car ownership (cheap parking/company incentives, etc.).

Possible solutions:

- Develop more use cases and recommendations;
- Avoid market fragmentation and foster global cooperation – or a 'global' approach;
- Promotion of MaaS solutions as :
 - A solution that changes lifestyle to a better quality level;
 - A solution that can improve an image of public transport (MaaS = Netflix, Amazon, etc.);
 - A better solution/offer than car ownership.
- Public Transport Authorities (PTAs) and Public Transport Operators (PTOs) can stay at the centre of data orchestration;

¹⁷ People with reduced mobility

- Collaboration across sectors (e.g., with energy, housing & building services) in order to receive additional value and better combinations of shared data;
- Put more attention to legislation for data management: there should be a clear definition of how data can be used, to whom it can/can't be sold, monopolies' regulation;
- Change the existing framework: e.g., increase car ownership costs (e.g., parking), introduce more restrictions for car use; this way increase revenue streams for MaaS schemes;

Support public transport by subsidising and introducing tax breaks.

6.4 Presentations from the workshop

Presentations from the workshop of other participants (key-note presentation and presentation of the involved projects) can be found in Appendices.

7 Formation and engagement of the stakeholder's group

Contact with stakeholders will be maintained through the Shift2MaaS website, Twitter, private LinkedIn Group, and via regular news-flashes as well as the regular UITP Newsletters. All relevant stakeholder groups will be invited to attend key project events and demonstrations, discussing Shift2MaaS activities and results. This will enable the project to gather feedback from specific perspectives. The stakeholders' engagement process is described in Shift2MaaS D5.2 Dissemination & exploitation strategy and activities.

In order to be a member of the stakeholder's group, invitees have to register on the Shift2MaaS website¹⁸:

Want to stay up date on Shift2MaaS and upcoming events? Login to your account to access additional information, or register to subscribe to the Shift2MaaS newsletter!

LOGIN TO YOUR ACCOUNT ▾

NOT A MEMBER YET? REGISTER NOW^

* First Name

* Family Name

* Email

* Company

I wish to be included in the project Newsletter and be notified about events and other news.

* I authorise you to handle my personal data within the scope of this registration form, as stated above.

* I Accept GDPR policy. [GDPR policy](#)

REGISTER

Figure 1: Registration to the stakeholder's zone

Registered members of the stakeholder's group will get access to all relevant information. They will all receive an invitation to the next stakeholder meetings.

Also, a Shift2MaaS LinkedIn Group has been set up to have informal discussions. LinkedIn is a business and employment-oriented social media platform. The LinkedIn Group will serve as another platform where consortium members and all other relevant stakeholders can share content, discuss project progress, or be updated on relevant industry developments. The LinkedIn group is closed, which means that users have to request access to join the group before being able to access the content. UITP will be in charge of accepting these requests.

All interested stakeholders will be invited to join this group.

Special attention will be paid to the stakeholders in the demonstration locations: other operators, organising authorities, travel services, etc. that are not yet a part of the Shift2MaaS project.

¹⁸ <http://shift2maas.eu/home.aspx>

Figure 2: the Shift2MaaS LinkedIn Group

The next offline workshop is planned:

Meeting	Month	Topics of discussion
2 nd Shift2MaaS stakeholders workshop	M19	Evaluation of work done and further exploitation of the results

Table 2: Schedule for the next stakeholder's workshop

8 Conclusions

This deliverable provides an overview of the Shift2MaaS stakeholders, clarifies the formation of the group, and sets out how the stakeholders' group will be engaged throughout the project's lifetime. Also, the deliverable reports on the already organised workshop on MaaS technologies, which took place during the UITP Summit.

The work with Shift2MaaS stakeholders will be continued until the end of the project, so the outcomes of this work will be included in D5.6 Final Stakeholders consultation report and additional use-cases.

9 References

GOF4R, D2.2 Analysis of the demand of market actors for the Interoperability Framework

Shift2MaaS, D5.2 Dissemination & exploitation strategy and activities

10 Appendices

Appendix 1

Stakeholders Workshop on MaaS technologies

Joint workshop of Shift2MaaS, IMOVE, Galileo4Mobility, My-TRAC and SMARTE

12 June 2019, 8:30 - 11:25

Stockholmsmässan, Mässvägen 1, 125 30 Älvsjö, Stockholm, Sweden

Meeting organiser	Daria Kuzmina, Guido Di Pasquale, Michele Tozzi (UITP)
Phone number	+32- 2 788 01 23

Concept

Key stakeholders active in the MaaS ecosystem are invited to discuss the increasing adoption of integrated mobility platforms across Europe and the commitment of selected EU-funded projects in supporting this process by addressing main barriers like interoperability among different schemes, data sharing and analytics, and accuracy of location-based services.

The projects Galileo4Mobility, IMOVE, My-TRAC, Shift2MaaS and SMARTE (co-funded under H2020 programme), even though different, are all testing advanced solutions for enhancing MaaS deployment and operation and their underlying business models. The knowledge gained in their unique pilots and research activities will kick off the discussion on issues such as

- Technical enablers, synergies and remaining barriers;
- Business models and strategies for exploitation and market uptake of MaaS schemes;
- Sustainability impacts MaaS should aim to deliver and how can these be assessed
- Data-sharing and analytics.

Agenda

Time	Topic
08:00 – 08:30	Welcome
08:30 – 08:45	Key note speech Martin RÖHRLEEF, Head of Mobility Innovation ÜSTRA Hannover
08:45 – 09:30	Positioning, ambitions and preliminary results of projects: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • IMOVE (Marco Gorini, Softeco) • Galileo4Mobility (Marti Jofre, Pildo) • My-TRAC (Ismeni Stroumpou, Aethon) • Shift2MaaS (João Vieira, CARRIS) • COHESIVE (Marco Ferreira, Thales) • SMARTE (Daniel Johnson, Leeds University)
09:30 – 09:45	Coffee break
09:45 – 10:45	Round tables: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Technical enablers (moderated by Marco Ferreira, Thales) • Market uptake (moderated by Marti Jofre, Pildo) • Impact assessment (moderated by Hans Arby, UbiGo) • Data-sharing (moderated by Simone Köhler, Siemens)
10:45 – 11:25	Debriefing and panel discussion Moderator: Guido Di Pasquale, UITP <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Marco Ferreira, Thales • Marti Jofre, Pildo • Hans Arby, UbiGo • Simone Köhler, Siemens • Esther Bravo, Shift2Rail JU

Ready for MaaS?

Easier mobility for citizens and better data for cities

Martin Röhrleef

ÜSTRA Hannoversche Verkehrsbetriebe AG
Head of Mobility Innovation

 @TwitterAccount

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UITP MAAS REPORT
&
POLICY BRIEF

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2

WHAT IS MAAS? - UITP DEFINITION

*Mobility as a Service (MaaS) is the integration of, and access to, different transport services in one single digital mobility offer **with active mobility and an efficient public transport system as its basis.***

*This tailor made service suggests the most suitable solutions based on the user's travel needs. MaaS is available anytime and offers integrated planning, booking and payment, as well as, en route information to provide **easy mobility and enable life without owning a car.***

WHY IS MAAS INTERESTING?

1. **Mega trends in mobility are boosting MaaS**
2. **Advantages for all stakeholders**

- **User:** complete and easy mobility
- **City:** helps to shape travel behaviour towards more sustainable modes
- **PT:** more customers and higher revenues

CREATING A USER CENTRIC EXPERIENCE

Usability and Trust are the keywords

- **Simplicity:** easy, user-friendly, convenient service
- **High quality:** correct information, reliability
- **Impartiality:** present mobility options in a transparent way
- **Flexibility:** personalized service adapted to customer needs
- **EXTRA VALUE**

BUILDING A STRONG PARTNERSHIP

MaaS is all about collaboration

- There must be a value for every partner
- Reciprocity & data deals
- Providers may keep their customer relationship

WHO TAKES WHICH ROLE WITHIN THE ECO-SYSTEM?

7

ROLE OF THE INTEGRATOR

WHO CAN MAKE IT FLY?

THE IMPACT ON
SUSTAINABLE
MOBILITY

=

**POSITIVE EFFECTS
PER CAPITA**

MODAL SHIFT
REDUCED CAR OWNERSHIP
MORE MOBILITY OPTIONS
BETTER AIR QUALITY
IMPROVED TRANSPORT QUALITY
EFFICIENT ENERGY USE

X

UTILISATION

NUMBER OF USERS

DIFFERENT MAAS MODELS

9

CONCLUSION

- MaaS will become **the future business model** in transportation
- MaaS can be a **brilliant tool for more sustainable mobility**
 - if deployed around mass public transport & active modes
- **Different approaches** possible

**Let's make sure MaaS is the desired tool that cities
can use to build a more sustainable future!**

RECOMMENDATIONS

Setting up successful MaaS solutions

- **Start to build the eco-system**
- Ensure **public transport and active mobility options are at the centre** of any MaaS solution
- Care about **data reciprocity & data protection**
- **Make use of the data** to optimize the urban mobility offer
- Adopt and harmonise **quality standards for all mobility providers**
- Foster **innovation** by funding

RECOMMENDATIONS

Build up institutional and policy integration

- Overcome institutional fragmentation with **mobility agencies or multimodal transport authorities** in charge of all urban mobility services
- Encourage **multimodal urban planning** for the development of mobility hubs and multimodal infrastructure
- Include **MaaS as a catalyst to reach policy goals** (SDG)

RECOMMENDATIONS

Create the right framework to promote MaaS

- **Stop wrong incentives that support car use** and thus hinder sustainable mobility behaviour and MaaS (free parking, company cars, ...)
- **Increase measures to limit car use** (access restrictions, road pricing, parking restrictions, street reclaiming...)
- Invest in digital solutions that **promote integration and openness.**

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UITP MAAS REPORT & POLICY BRIEF

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14

A blue poster with white and yellow text. The main title is 'GALILEO FOR MOBILITY' in large white letters, with a yellow dot above the 'i' and yellow signal waves to the right. Below it is the subtitle 'Fostering the adoption of Galileo for Mobility as a Service'. At the bottom, there are logos for the European Union and the European Global Navigation Satellite Systems Agency, along with a funding acknowledgment.

GALILEO
FOR MOBILITY

Fostering the adoption of Galileo
for Mobility as a Service

European
Global Navigation
Satellite Systems
Agency

This project has received funding from the European Global Navigation Satellite Systems Agency under grant agreement No 776381

GALILEO, an enabler for improved MaaS

GALILEO
FOR MOBILITY

Estimpo am facie Sater
quam eris dokupit saequae
con cum fiet roivewet

PARTNERS

GALILEO is Europe's own global navigation satellite system, providing a highly accurate, guaranteed global positioning service under civilian control. Currently providing Initial Services, GALILEO is interoperable with GPS and Glonass, the US and Russian global satellite navigation systems.

BENEFITS FOR MaaS:

- Increased availability
 - Better accuracy
 - Lower Time-To-First-Fix
-

OBJECTIVES

- 1** UNDERSTAND, DEFINE AND VALIDATE THE REQUIREMENTS FOR GALILEO IN MOBILITY AS A SERVICE (MAAS)
- 2** DEVELOP THE KEY ELEMENTS TO EXPLOIT GALILEO BENEFITS
- 3** DISSEMINATE THE PROJECT RESULTS AND SUPPORT THEIR EXPLOITATION AFTER THE PROJECT LIFETIME

Pilots Barcelona

**Public transport
on demand**

MaaS aggregator

**Autonomous vehicle
on campus**

Pilot Paris

Vehicle sharing

Pilot Thessaloniki

Shared taxis

WWW.GALILEO4MOBILITY.EU

 @galileomobility

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IMOVE Project Overview

Marco Gorini, Softeco Sismat SRL

12/06/2019

1

I simply want to move. I want to move simply

IMOVE received funding by the European Union's
Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
under grant agreement number 723314

IMOVE

Unlocking Large-Scale Access to Combined Mobility through a European MaaS Network

Project Synopsis:

- o Innovative concepts, systems and services towards 'mobility as a service'
 - MG-6.1-2016 call, one of the three selected projects (IMOVE, MaaS4EU, MyCorridor)
- o Research and Innovation Action (RIA)
 - 30 months duration: 1.06.2017 - 30.11.2019
 - 3.69 M€ cost, 3.39 M€ EU grant
- o Consortium: 15 organizations, 6 countries
 - research: AICENTER (CVUT), I-SENSE (ICCS), RISE
 - ICT/consulting: Softeco Sismat, Mosaic Factor, FIT, V
 - mobility: Transport for Greater Manchester, 5T, Municipality of Turin, UBIGO, URBI, Vasttrafik, EMT Madrid
 - stakeholders' association: UITP

12/06/2019

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I simply want to move. I want to move simply

Objective and key challenges

To accelerate the deployment and unlock the scalability of MaaS schemes in Europe, paving the way for a "roaming" service for MaaS users at the European level

Main streams of research:

o Measures, Policies and Strategies

- Heterogeneous organizational/regulatory frameworks, unclear business models → **Scalability Unlockers:** to ease the framework conditions for MaaS development and operation (business models, guidelines, best practices)

o Enabling Technologies

- A broad offer of services/products already on the market (mobile apps, travel planners, e-ticketing, APIs, MaaS Platforms) → **Software Enablers:** to integrate existing functionalities, enhance interoperability and facilitate

12/06/2019

I simply want to move. I want to move simply
cross-border roaming of MaaS schemes

Tech enablers: the IMOVE Software Enablers

Modular “building blocks” wrapped around basic MaaS functions

- Can be «chained» together to support various MaaS operational tasks

o Lay down a common framework to ease interoperability between

12/06/2019

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Validating MaaS enablers: the IMOVE demo sites

A mix of transport environments: metropolitan / mid-size urban / rural areas

“Living Lab” approach: involvement of local stakeholders

Roaming across sites/operators

Göteborg

MaaS provider: local providers (SpaceTime SmartResenär) + Västtrafik
 Integration Level: initial L0, target L2-L3-L4
 3 distinct pilots: PT + parking services (integrated ticketing); combined mobility solutions for residents/ tenants (132 new apartments with combined mobility services instead of parking); B2B combined mobility for business trips

Berlin

MaaS provider: URBI (IMOVE partner)
 Integration Level: initial L1, target L2
 integration of at least one MSP per transport mode. Cooperation with PT: adaptation of APIs for integrated ticketing system, reselling of PT tickets through URBI app

Turin

MaaS provider: URBI (IMOVE partner)
 Integration Level: initial L1, target L2
 Focus on home-2-work / work-2-work mobility: General Motors employees + Municipality employees. Strong role of PT (GTT), engagement of private MSP (car-/bike-sharing) ongoing

Manchester

MaaS provider: Mobilleo
 Integration Level: initial L0, target L3 (medium term)
 Several focus groups with local stakeholders (MSPs, users). Analysis of potentially applicable business models (public vs private)

Madrid

MaaS provider: EMT Madrid (proprietary platform)
 Integration Level: initial L1, target L2 (+ policy integration)
 “MaaS Madrid” project as part of the Action Plan of the City: PT, Car-Sharing, Scooter-sharing, Bike-Sharing, PMV

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Lessons Learned (so far)

MaaS is a very promising transport paradigm, but there are still barriers that slow down the fulfillment of its full potential:

- Level of market readiness (expectations vs. practicalities)
- Perception of risks and uncertainties among ecosystem actors
- Agreements between public and private MSPs (car-/bike-sharing, taxis) may be slower than planned
- Timing of tendering processes
- Challenges related to existing institutional frameworks

Key Enablers:

- Role of Public Transport Authorities is crucial for a calibrated and trustable offering
- Substantial readiness of technology (core levels L1-L3)
- Engagement of MaaS tech providers from the start of the initiative
- Collaboration (e.g. sharing of information) between MaaS experiences

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Thank you

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UNLOCKING LARGE-SCALE ACCESS
TO COMBINED MOBILITY THROUGH
A EUROPEAN MAAS NETWORK

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IMOVE received funding by the European Union's
Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme
under grant agreement number 723314

D5.5 Interim Stakeholder
consultation report

Contract No. 826252

Appendix 5

Grant Agreement Number: H2020 – 777640

My-TRAC for UITP summit

June 11, 2019

Ismeni Stroumpou

AETHON Engineering Consultants P.C

07/09/2017

1

01/08/2019

52

Starting Date: 1/9/2017
Duration: 37 months

Grant agreement ID: 777640
Overall budget: € 3 494 476,25

UPC	EXPERIS	USAL
AETHON	AMETRO	CERTH
DUT		
STRA		
UITP		

CONSORTIUM

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07/09/2017

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My-TRAC

My-TRAC + MaaS

My-TRAC + MaaS

GTFS from TSPs

3rd parties data (e.g.
parking, events)

Map of My-TRAC technologies

07/09/2017

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What next?

- Pilots of My-TRAC

07/09/2017

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WP3 - T3.3 presentation

What the passenger really wants:

rail user centric planning and mobility

UITP Global Public Transport Summit

Motivation

- Work Package 3 of SMaRTE aims to understand current and future needs of railway passengers.
- Findings presented here based on Passenger surveys conducted as part of Task 3.3.

Aims of task

- To identify aspects of the rail traveller's experience which could be improved and simplified through information / mobility support.
- To quantify potential passengers lost at each phase of the journey

Methodology

Literature review (D3.1) , stakeholder and passenger consultations identified:

- emerging 'macro trends'
 - physical and planning factors associated with rail journey phases.
 - these fed into an Experience Map (D3.2)
-
- Quantitative analysis of recent rail passenger journey experiences in 3 case study areas to identify levels of **importance** and **satisfaction** with these factors amongst 3 key passenger groups – students/commuters/retired.
 - Using **non-rail** journeys to identify attrition rates for each activity in the journey which quantify potential customers lost at each phase of the journey

Data Collection

- Conducted survey on 1,200 representative transport users in Rome, Leeds/Manchester and Brussels, with questions on:
 - Attitudes
 - Socio-economic background/personal characteristics
 - Recent rail trips and associated satisfaction and importance ratings.
 - Recent non-rail trips and required improvements to switch to rail

Results: Importance ratings

- Cost of ticket is the principle consideration for rail journeys
- Ability to book journeys in advance, ability to find a seat and security and safety more important factors than time related elements.
- Journey planning tools also important facilitators.

Results: Satisfaction ratings

- Over 80% of rail travellers reported journeys as satisfactory or better.

- Retired passengers most likely to be 'very satisfied' (31%) whilst commuters have higher levels of dissatisfaction
- Perhaps these passenger types experience the services at different times, but also perhaps they have different expectations.

- Most dissatisfaction with car parking cost and availability, cleanliness and maintenance of the station, ticket costs, wi-fi and power connectivity and availability/frequency of services of out of peak times.
- Car parking cost (26%) and availability (20%) a particular concern for retired.
- Cost is a principle source of dissatisfaction for commuters (20%).
- For students, connectivity in vehicles (18%) and at stations (21%) concerns.
- Car parking cost and service availability was a particular issue for Brussels.
- Rome happy with costs.
- UK passengers show lower levels of dissatisfaction except with ticket cost, car parking availability and reliability.

Results: Non-rail journeys

- Cost primary factor requiring ‘improvement’
- Other key considerations include non-service level related factors eg on board security and safety and ability to find a seat.
- These are not key sources of dissatisfaction from actual journeys -perhaps indicates a ‘gap’ between perceptions of rail and actual experiences of passengers.

Conclusions

- Clearly the rail experience is not just about what happens on board!
- Cost is primary concern in terms of importance, satisfaction and non-users. Beyond that, other factors aside from journey time and reliability emerge as key determinants of journey experience
- So whilst not specifically about MaaS, through our findings elements of the MaaS concept are clearly important considerations for passengers – role for apps here, ie planning tools and ability to book in advance are important.
- Access issues, cleanliness and connectivity emerge as key sources of dissatisfaction – perhaps not so difficult to address as time related elements.
- Perception gap between users and non-users regarding ability to find seat and security could be addressed through information/marketing/branding
- Next steps include validation of findings with industry experts then recommendations on how to decrease physical and cognitive effort through a “Smart Journey Vision” and rail map of measures.
- ***Note these are provisional findings and work not yet accepted by commission***

**Thank you for your
attention, from WP3 team!**

Partners:

Project coordinator:

UNIVERSITY OF LEEDS

